

APPENDIX A – QUESTIONS ASKED THROUGH THE FALA.BR PLATFORM

1. after the publication of Decree No. 9,203/2017, is there a Risk Management Plan?
2. Is there an Integrity Plan after the publication of Decree No. 9,203/2017 or Decree No. 11,529/2023?
3. If you have the Risk Management Plan and/or Integrity Plan, do they include risks related to integrity according to the concept outlined in Ordinance 57/2019 of the CGU?
 - 3.1 If yes, could you describe how these risks are defined?
 - 3.2 If yes, how are they being managed?
 - 3.3 If yes, how is the information derived from integrity risk management used and integrated into decision-making by this agency? Provide examples of how this information influences decisions.
4. Besides Risk Management Plans, is there evidence of this Plan's practical and effective implementation? How is this implementation verified or evaluated within the agency?

Note: Please attach the Plans to the Platform or provide a link to download them. Any other documents that demonstrate this agency's concern with Risk Management (e.g., policy, program, ordinances, code of ethics or conduct, manuals, guides, etc.) may be attached to the response.